

QUIZ**LAST NAME: UMEH****FIRST NAME: GREGORY****PROGRAM CODE: MIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice 2010, window 8

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- We do research every time we ask questions and look for evidence or facts to answer them. Which of the following options best represent the order of events in research? Tick the correct answer.**
 - Report writing, data collection, publication, observation, and questioning.
 - Questioning, publication, data collection, observation, and report writing.
 - Observation, questioning, data collection, report writing, and publication.¹**
 - Publication, report writing, observation, questioning, and data collection.

¹ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers.*, ed. University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff Wayne Booth, Gregory Colomb, Joseph Williams, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 15.

2. **Researchers ask three primary types of questions to understand a problem and know what to do. Which of the following options represent the right questions? Tick the correct answer.**
- Conceptual questions, physical questions and intellectual questions.
 - Conceptual questions, practical questions and applied questions.²**
 - Practical questions, long questions and short questions.
 - Applied questions, difficult questions and easy questions.
3. **A researcher must be familiar with essential elements like composing sentences, combing sentences, building paragraphs, and writing essays. The researcher should avoid the following common errors except? Tick the correct answer.**
- References.³**
 - Fragmentation of sentences.
 - Wordy sentence.
 - Run-on sentence.
4. **A researcher must give credit to the works of others. The refusal to provide credit may lead to plagiarism. Which of the following is another reason for citing the works of other writers? Tick the correct answer.**

² Turabian, 16.

³ EUCLID, "ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1 Essay Writing," *Euclid University*, 2015, 1-7.

- Entertain readers.
- Make things easy for readers.
- Increase the length of the manuscript.
- Assure readers about the accuracy of the facts.**⁴

5. **Researchers must be familiar with citation and referencing styles. Which of the following is the two commonest referencing style? Tick the correct answer.**

- Reference style and footnotes style.
- Note style and bibliography style.
- Note-bibliography style and author-date style.**⁵
- Footnotes style and endnotes style.

6. **Which of the following represents the consequences of plagiarism? Tick the correct answer.**

- Ethical and unacceptable offense.
- Unethical and serious academic offense.**⁶
- Wrong and acceptable offense.
- Ethical and pardonable offense.

⁴ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 85-87.

⁵ Turabian, 85-87.

⁶ Turabian, 86.

7. **The “Chicago Style” of writing was made famous by which of the following authors? Tick the correct answer.**

Patrick Sabranek.

Dave Kemper.

Kate Turabian.⁷

Verne Meyer.

8. **The WHO house style is the preferred spelling, punctuation, terminology, and formatting to be used for the various information and products published by WHO. Which of the following represent where and the year it was published? Tick the correct answer.**

Geneva, 2006.

Geneva, 2004.⁸

New York, 2004.

London, 2004.

9. **The Harvard style of citing and referencing is one of several styles of referencing and bibliographic citation that is used widely in academic writing. Which of the following best represents it? Tick the correct answer.**

⁷ Turabian, 10.

⁸ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004), 1-2.

- Note-bibliography style.
- Footnotes style.
- Endnotes style.
- Author-date style.**⁹

10. **Many universities have their style. Which of the following represents the style of a well-known university in the United Kingdom?**

- Chicago style.
- Harvard style.
- Oxford style.**¹⁰
- Sydney style.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1 Essay Writing*. Euclid University, 2015.
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<http://www.eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401-period-5/>. Accessed 31 July 2019.

⁹ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 4* (EUCLID, 2015), 73.

¹⁰ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 4* (EUCLID, 2015), 30.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.